

What is nonverbal behavior (communication) ?

Hand movements

Nonverbal behavior can be defined as any kind of movements the human body produces whether accompanied by speech or not ,voluntary or involuntary, and which serves a communicative purpose or could be interpreted as a sign of a psychological or emotional state of an individual.

The importance of nonverbal behavior

Nonverbal behavior (communication) plays an important role in our lives. It is like what Birdwhistell says in (Birdwhistell,1970) Cited in(Feyereisen & De lannoy, 1991,p 2) " Human communication consists, in equal proportions, of verbal and nonverbal behavior."

This is because, one rarely finds a person who speaks without producing any kind of body movements or gestures. And the same thing can be said about listeners or speakers during moments of silence.

Body movements and gestures, whether accompanied by speech or not, have become almost an integrated part of humans' communicative system . As Geddes and Grosset say in (Geddes & Grosset, 1996, p 115) " It would be difficult to prevent our selves from making voluntary gestures ... Because they have become a habit with us and are often part of the convention of communication. It would be even more difficult to cure our selves of involuntary gestures."

This could tell the reader how much people tend to use gestures and rely on them, whether planned or not, till they have become life long habits.

Gestures could be of much benefit to the speaker since they could make his speech less condensed.

This could be done with the help of illustrative gestures e.g. drawing shapes in the air or pointing to certain things and directions. This is because as Wundt says in (Wundt,1973) Cited in (Feyereisen & De lannoy, 1991,p 2) " In some respects, gestures are considered to have the property of expressing the content of consciousness as words do."

A further explanation is presented by Kendon in (Kendon, 1986) Cited in (Feyereisen & De lannoy, 1991,p 2) " This means, in contemporary terms, that gestures and words both relate to the mental representations that constitute thinking."

Another role which nonverbal behavior plays is the relief it gives to the individual from emotional tensions which could be a great threat to his physical and psychological health.

According to Zajonc's [Vascular Theory of Emotional Efference] in (Zajonc,1985) cited in (Zanna,1996, p: 391)

The actions of the facial musculature that produce facial expressions of emotions serve to restrict venous flow, thereby impeding or facilitating the cooling of cerebral blood as it enters the brain. The resulting variations in cerebral temperature, Zajonc hypothesizes, promote or inhibit the release of emotion-linked neurotransmitters, which in turn, affect subjective emotional experience.

This kind of information will probably make people pay greater attention and care to nonverbal behavior issues.

In addition, interpreting nonverbal behavior could be very helpful in determining the psychological and emotional state of an individual and in facilitating the communication process between this individual and other individuals accompanying him . Because if they know his psychological and emotional state, they will know how to deal with him and how to manage the communication process.

One could ask how does nonverbal behavior provide us with such information? Or why does it have such a revealing power?

The answer is as Geddes and Grosset have put it in (i bid, p: 241) "The language we speak is often qualified by a subconscious body language that can be a truer indication of how we really feel. Learning about this ... can help us to interpret other people's true feelings and to understand more about what our own gestures reveal about ourselves."

Interpreting nonverbal behavior

One might wonder how could he reach correct interpretations of gestures and body movements. According to Feyereisen and De lannoy in (i bid,p:43) "The meaning of a movement is defined by the context in which it is performed and/or by the response of another individual perceiving the movement."

This means that one cannot fix the meaning of a certain movement or generalize it on various contexts. Besides, one cannot say that different individuals will have the same interpretation for a particular body movement or gesture .

An example of how the meaning of a body movement or gesture could vary according to context is mentioned by Feyereisen and De lannoy (i bid) ; but the example originally belongs to a study by Sherzer in (Sherzer,1973) on a pointing gesture which is used by the Cuna Indians in Panama.

The gesture consists of head raising, looking in a specific direction, mouth opening, and lip protrusion. It can be observed in several contexts: 1- raising or answering questions about location or direction, 2- commands or declarative statements with a possessive or demonstrative meaning, 3- joking with or teasing the target person, 4- greeting. In each case, the gesture may be performed alone or with a spoken utterance. Thus, it may play diverse roles according to the circumstances, and correct interpretation requires information on context and rather sophisticated inferences.

Concerning involuntary movements or gestures, it could be difficult to interpret them. This is due to the fact that they cannot be noticed easily and they actually express something which the speaker is trying to hide. (Geddes & Grosset, 1996).

Some times, an individual produces more than one gesture or movement at a time. This is called a cluster.

A cluster could facilitate the interpretation of body movements and gestures since it helps in creating a back ground against which those movements could be interpreted. An example of how the interpretation of a gesture changes if it occurs in a cluster is mentioned by Geddes and Grosset (i bid) " A sitting position involving tightly crossed legs conveys a defensive attitude, but if the person also has his head and chin down, then the defensive position becomes one of hostility."

Kinds of nonverbal behavior

Nonverbal behavior could be classified under the following categories: head movements, facial expressions, hand movements, leg movements, and posture.

Facial movements consist of lip movements, eyes movements, and eye brows movements.

As for hand movements, they include hand-arm movements and finger movements.

The hand could have a part in other body movements e.g. touching parts of the face, and touching the head.

Concerning the body posture, it is the general view of the whole human body's state including its different parts at a particular time.

This paper is going to focus on hand movements including their emergence, types, and functions.

The emergence of gesture in infancy

A newly born child will mainly depend on his voice (crying) to attract people's attention so that they fulfill his needs. At this stage the child could barely make any communicative gestures.

Later, at the age of 8-12 weeks the child becomes aware of his body parts and tries to move them and usually this will be accompanied by random noises and cries produced by the child which will later develop in to a clear and comprehensible speech. This is further explained by Trevarthen in (Trevarthen,1977) cited in (Feyereisen & De lannoy, 1991, p 117)

As early as the age of 8-12 weeks, hand and finger movements are synchronized with prespeech movements, namely, small facial movements like tongue protrusion and lip contraction which are interpreted by the mother as attempts to talk . These facial movements, which are usually produced without concurrent vocalization, are accompanied by hand, foot or trunk movements. Among these, hand and arm movements, especially hand waving, finger pointing, and finger tip claspings, are very finely synchronized with prespeech movements with a window of 0,1 sec. Thus, there seems to be an innate basis for the coordination of manual and oral movements .

Note that the afore mentioned hand and finger movements could be described as random and almost meaningless. But later at the age of 9 months, the child learns how to express his intention or desire to have something through the use of a communicative pointing gesture.

Vygotsky in (Vygotsky,1970) cited in (Lock,1978,p:160) has explained through his theory that the child's communicative pointing gesture has originally evolved from an unsuccessful attempt to grasp or reach an object . The child's attempt was interpreted by his mother as a message sent to her in order to help the child to get the object. So, she brings the child the object. This whole incident has made the child realize that his pointing gesture can be a communicative signal which attracts people's attention.

Types of hand movements

Kendon (1983) cited in (Zanna,1996) has suggested an arrangement of hand movements according to what degree they resemble words whether in the semantic content or the communicative function. Thus, depending on this suggestion Chawla, Chen and Krauss (Zanna,1996) have presented the following classification of hand movements.

1- ADAPTERS: These are not considered gestures but rather manipulations either of the person or of some object e.g. scratching, rubbing, and touching.

They are also said to be non communicative, not intentional and not related to the speech they accompany. However, they can be expressive forms of the speaker's psychological and emotional state.

Other suggested terms for this type of gestures are: expressive movements (Reuschert, 1909), body focused movements (Freedman & Hoffman, 1967), self touching gestures (kimura, 1970), manipulative gestures (Edelman & Hampson, 1979), self manipulators (Rosenfeld, 1966), and contact acts (Bull & Connelly, 1985).

2- SYMBOLIC GESTURES: This type has a communicative content and it is considered to be intentionally used.

Usually these gestures have a conventional meaning which is agreed upon by a certain society e.g. "thumbs-up" and "bye- bye".

Although these gestures are usually not accompanied by speech , they can also be used during speech either as an extra emphasis or a substitution for an unsaid word.

These gestures have other terms like: emblems (Efron, 1941), autonomous gestures (Kendon, 1983), conventionalized signs (Reuschert, 1909), formal pantomimic gestures (Wiener, Devoe, Rubinow & Celler, 1972), expressive gestures (Zinober & Martlew, 1985), and semiotic gestures (Barakat, 1973).

3-CONVERSATIONAL GESTURES: This type of gestures is neither devoid of meaning as the adapters, nor resembles words in the communicative function or the semantic content as the symbolic gestures.

Conversational gestures are related in form to the speech they accompany .

Other suggested terms for conversational gestures are: illustrators (Ekman & Friesen, 1972) and signifying signs (Reuschert, 1909).

Hadar (1989) cited in (Zanna, 1996, P 394) has suggested two subcategories of conversational gestures which are: motor movements and lexical movements.

MOTOR MOVEMENTS: repeated fixed movements which are used in positions of stressed syllables of speech. They don't seem related to the content of the speech.

Other suggested terms for this category are: batons (Efron, 1972) and beats (McNeill, 1987).

As for the functions of motor movements, some suggestions have been mentioned in (Zanna, 1996) "They exert a structuring influence in the control of discourse production (Rime, 1982); they disambiguate syntax (McClave, 1991); they serve as " extra narrative comments" (McNeil & Levy, 1982); they reflect the organization of the discourse (Kendon, 1980)."

As for the function of disambiguating syntax, it is a common thing that people tend to produce repetitive movements when they try to make their sentences clearer to their listeners and when they get involved in narratives.

LEXICAL MOVEMENTS: These movements are related to the content of the accompanying speech, non repetitive, and changing in form and length.

The main function of these movements is helping the speaker in word retrieval from the mental lexicon during speech e.g. when a speaker wants to use the word vortex and before uttering it in its verbal shape, he makes a gesture that signifies motion and circularity which are also part of the semantic content of the word vortex (Zanna, 1996).

Thus, this gesture has helped the speaker keep in his mind the conceptual properties of the word that he was looking for until he found it (Hadar & Butterworth, 1993) cited in (Zanna, 1996).

In addition, lexical movements could aid the speaker in the conceptualization of the intended message. This means that if a person wants to describe something like how he had hit the ball in a tennis match for example, performing the act again will help him in formulating his verbal message since it will make him remember the exact steps of his action (Zanna, 1996).

Interpretations of some hand movements

In this section a sample of suggested interpretations by Geddes and Grosset (1996) for different hand movements will be presented.

Basically, the interpreted movements belong to the adapters category. But, usually most of the movements are not accompanied by speech.

It will be noticed how these movements tend to communicate psychological information rather than semantic information. So, these movements could be a true unconscious expression of the individual's mind and emotions.

Geddes and Grosset suggest that if a listener's head is in a neutral position but his hand is touching his cheek or may be rubbing it slightly then, he could be weighing up what the speaker has said before telling him his decision .If the listener is stroking his chin with his index and thumb and forming a "v" shape while doing so then, he is thinking deeply.

Another movement is head scratching which indicates that the person is puzzled or bewildered by something.

Concerning head slapping, it indicates that the performer of this movement has suddenly realized that he has forgotten something important or has remembered it too late.

As for supporting the head with the hand while the elbow is leaning on a table, it indicates that the person is either tired or extremely bored.

Clasping the hands behind the head is an indicator that the person is far from being nervous and do not feel threatened by any thing nor afraid of any thing. Usually it is people of authority who frequently perform this movement. This movement could be performed by either sex while having a break from work or after finishing a work which makes them feel confident and pleasant about what they have achieved .

It is common for people to touch their hair, press it or twist it when they are nervous. In addition, running one's hands through his hair is a sign of desperation, frustration, and anger.

Placing the hand on the eyebrow could have many interpretations according to the context in which it was performed e.g. being worried, anxious or tired.

The following two movements (rubbing the ear lobe, touching the cheeks) are considered to be two signs of anxiety.

These other two movements (rubbing the nose, covering the mouth with the hand) are interpreted as signs of lying.

Placing the fingers in the mouth is a sign of insecurity, stress and pressure.

If a person is cupping his chin then, he could be in a state of deep contemplation.

Touching the neck could be interpreted as lying or being un comfortable . But if a person is clasping his neck, then this could be a sign of anger; while scratching the neck with the index and under the ear, could be a sign of uncertainty and doubts.

Clasping the hands is an indication of nervousness and clenching them is a sign of tension and self restraining; while rubbing the hands is an indicator of anticipation.

Hands steeping indicates a state of contemplation and in certain contexts it indicates superiority.

Furthermore, lowered hand steeple could be regarded as a sign of a positive listener.

Pressing the hands together means that the speaker is emphasizing something or persuading someone.

Finally, thumb twiddling could have the following interpretations according to context: boredom, impatience or having nothing to do.

Conclusion

Thus, as it has been displayed throughout this paper, nonverbal behavior plays a very important role in humans' lives since it almost forms half of the human communication system and it adds vitality and flavor to their communicative activities.

However, one shouldn't think that any gesture he might have in mind is a universal one but, he should take into consideration that almost every speech community has its own special gestures. This brings us to the importance of specifying parts of language courses which take care of explaining some significant and special gestures which native speakers usually produce during speech in a certain language. This help non native speakers in avoiding countless misunderstandings.

References

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